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High-Fidelity “Top-Down” DLP Bioprinting of Multi-Material Soft Tissue Constructs Enabled by Computer Vision–Based Layer Control

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ABSTRACT

Bioprinting continues to redefine the frontiers of regenerative medicine by enabling the fabrication of complex, three-dimensional tissue constructs that emulate native biological and mechanical functions. However, despite significant progress, critical challenges remain, particularly in achieving precise multi-material integration, high-resolution patterning, and structural fidelity necessary for functional tissue engineering. A major limitation in “top-down” vat photopolymerization bioprinting, especially Digital Light Processing (DLP)-based approaches, lies in the precise control of layer thickness, a parameter that directly affects mechanical integrity, biological activity, and spatial resolution. This study presents a novel, automated platform designed to overcome one of the most persistent bottlenecks in multi-material top-down DLP bioprinting: the real-time, accurate measurement of the dynamic gap between the cured layer and the bioink surface. Through a comparative assessment of classical computer vision and deep learning (CNN-based) techniques, we demonstrate a system capable of achieving sub-0.1 mm precision (0.092 mm) with strong correlation to mechanical measurements ($R = 0.994$). This vision-based system adapts to a wide range of bioinks with varying viscosities, opacities, and photopolymerization kinetics, eliminating the need for manual recalibration during material switching. As a demonstration of its capabilities, we successfully printed a multimaterial vascular-like tissue structure with high spatial fidelity across heterogeneous biomaterials. Further, we bioprinted a multimaterial skin tissue model, featuring compartmentalized dermal/bone analogs, to enable *in vitro* functional evaluation. These case studies highlight the platform's potential to advance biofabrication workflows by improving reproducibility, material adaptability, and structural precision, paving the way toward clinically scalable tissue manufacturing systems.

Keywords: *3D bioprinting, computer vision, Multimaterial bioprinting, Digital light processing, artificial intelligence, vat photopolymerization*

1. Introduction

3D Bioprinting is an emergent technology that allows the generation of tissues that incorporate a variety of cell types in a complex and defined spatial architecture to mimic human tissue physiology [1]. The potential of generating transplantable tissue structures using bioprinting technologies has also grown with the development of new biomaterials and bioprinting processes, which has been demonstrated in various tissue structures: vascular and nerve grafts, trachea, muscles, bone, cartilage, thyroid and heart tissue [2]. Notwithstanding the significant advances in 3D bioprinting, not a single artificial tissue has been used to replace a part of an organ, except for simple or avascular tissues like skin or cartilage [3]. This is principally due 3D bioprinting state-of-the-art technologies stem from the fact that the multi-scaled microstructures associated to the human living microtissues, and organs cannot be easily replicated, and as consequence, fail on developing functional and physiological real organs. The main technologies used for the bioprinting of biological materials and precisely deposition cell-laden technologies include contact-based and contactless methods [4]. The common contact-based methods are extrusion and inkjet printing. The main inconvenient of these technologies, especially extrusion, is associated to printing speed and the risk of needle clogging associated with high viscosity, which can expose the cells to high shear forces, resulting in cell death [5].

On the other hand, contactless methods include Light-based bioprinting technologies, including, laser-based technologies, Stereolithography (SLA) and Digital light processing (DLP) [6]. Among them, DLP which used ultraviolet (UV) light to solidify a photosensitive bioink in a layer-by-layer fashion to generate a 3D structure, has been demonstrated for generating high resolution tissue structures [7]. This technology involves using DLP projector to solidify a photosensitive liquid material, known as photopolymer, which is placed in a biomaterial container and a UV-DLP image projecting system generates, layer by layer, through a photochemical reaction the desired three-dimensional model. Each layer of the model to be printed is generated from a CAD model which is transformed into a stack of images of equally spaced layers or cross-sections, each of these images is sequentially projected by the DLP projector on the resin, creating a complete 3D replica of the original CAD model. Some of the most pertinent issues that arise during the construction process include the control of the resin surface level, material handling and material purity.

There are two major approaches to DLP bioprinting [8]: Top-down and Bottom-up. In top-down bioprinting the light is projected from the top and the platform is moved down into the vat after each layer is printed. In this case, the model is generated on a support platform, while in the Bottom-up bioprinting approach, the light is emitted into the bottom of the vat and the platform starts at the bottom, moving up after each layer. The model is created under the support platform.

On top-down printers, the layer thickness is determined by the gap between the model, which is on the platform and submersed along with it in the biomaterial and the height of the biomaterial which covers it. This gap (ranging from 20 to 100 micrometers) must be calculated precisely as it determines the layer height and therefore the correlation between the slicer of the object to be printed and the final printed object. This difference can be

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2 estimated by computing the volume of the platform, the calculated volume of the printed model and the initial
3 volume of the biomaterial. The problem that arises is that both the amount of biomaterial and the model's height
4 vary from layer to layer and this calculus can only be an estimation. In the existing literature, there are no
5 works that directly address this problem, with the closest one being the one developed by [9], where in a
6 multi-material DLP printer, a custom leveling system is used (including a laser displacement sensor, floating
7 target, peristaltic pump, pump head) with several configurations which facilitated adding and removing desired
8 quantities of resin to and from each vat [10]. The leveling system provided high accuracy (± 5 nm) control for
9 control for maintaining resin levels in the multiple vats. This procedure is difficult to implement due to the large
10 number of devices involved and it requires a printer with sufficient volume and maintenance that ensures all
11 elements can be located and precisely coordinated, which makes it hardly applicable in our case. However, the
12 gap can be calculated by visual inspection by a human operator using a camera located in the bioprinter and a
13 scale as a reference.

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21 In this sense, artificial intelligence (AI) is revealed as a potential tool to solve these problems. AI intelligence
22 is often linked to terms such as machine learning, neural network, automation or even computer vision. The
23 idea here is that a machine can solve a problem on its own, without human intervention, based on data and past
24 experiences. This is particularly interesting when combined with 3D bioprinting technologies, as it can increase
25 the performance of a 3D bioprinter by reducing the risk of error and facilitating automated production. This
26 work advances the field of multi-material digital light processing (DLP) bioprinting by addressing critical
27 challenges in process control, precision, and material characterization, focusing on solving the problem of
28 calculating the gap between the model/support height and the level of biomaterial covering it, which is one of
29 the fundamental problems of printing through top-down multi-material DLP bioprinters, with application to
30 bioprinting of tissues. The primary contributions are fivefold. First, we develop a novel, automated gap-control
31 platform for top-down multi-material DLP bioprinting that eliminates the need for manual recalibration during
32 material switching, thereby improving robustness and operational efficiency. Second, we conduct a rigorous
33 comparative evaluation between classical computer vision methods, specifically edge detection, and deep
34 learning architectures based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs), demonstrating that lightweight
35 algorithms achieve superior real-time performance—up to 60 frames per second—making them particularly
36 suitable for embedded control systems. Third, the proposed system attains sub-0.1 mm measurement precision
37 (0.092 mm) and shows a strong correlation ($R = 0.994$) with mechanical benchmark measurements across a
38 broad spectrum of bioink opacities and viscosities. Fourth, we validate the platform through the successful
39 fabrication of complex, multicellular tissue constructs, including a hierarchical vascular-like model and a
40 compartmentalized skin model, both exhibiting high cell viability. Finally, we present an optical and mechanical
41 characterization of tartrazine as a dual-purpose additive, demonstrating its effectiveness in simultaneously
42 controlling curing depth and modulating stiffness at multi-material interfaces.

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56 Section 2 of this work describes the materials and methods, including the experimental setup, AI-based liquid
57 level detection techniques used, and a detailed description of the algorithms developed as part of this research.
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2 Section 3 presents the results and discussion, showing experimental results both in terms of achieved
3 measurement precision and qualitative analysis of the manufactured objects. We have validated the developed
4 system for bioprinting complex, multimaterial constructs, including vascular-like tissue structures with
5 hierarchical organization and a multilayered skin tissue model. The results demonstrate that the platform is
6 capable of accurately depositing multiple cell-laden bioinks in well-defined spatial arrangements, while
7 maintaining high levels of cell viability and structural fidelity. These case studies confirm the robustness and
8 versatility of the printing and monitoring system for the fabrication of biologically relevant tissue constructs.
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10 Section 4 summarizes the conclusions reached in this work.
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16 **2. Materials and methods**

17 *2.1 Bioprinter*

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19 We have developed a custom stereolithographic multimaterial “top-down” 3D bioprinter (Figure 1). The
20 bioprinter consists of the following main components: (1) DLP projector: This component projects each layer of
21 the model to be printed into the biogel, enabling the polymerization process. The projector model used is the
22 Wintech PRO6600, with a 4K (3840 × 2160 pixels) resolution, 385 nm wavelength, and > 3000 mW power
23 output. (2) Printing platform: This is the platform on which the printed object is built. It is attached to a stepper
24 motor, allowing precise positioning on the Z axis. (3) Camera: Used for recording the printing process, it enables
25 both real-time analysis with computer vision techniques and the storage of videos for further study. The webcam
26 used is the ELP USB4KHDR01-KL100 model, capable of recording in 4K resolution. (4) Control computer:
27 This component controls all the printer’s components in a coordinated manner, allowing the user to manually
28 control them or set parameters and initiate the printing process through the integrated touch screen. The PC is
29 equipped with an AMD Ryzen 9 4900H CPU, clocked at 3.30 GHz, an integrated Radeon GPU, and 16 GB of
30 RAM.
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Figure 1: a) Diagram of the bioprinter top-down printing configuration, b) Schematic representation of the digital light projection system: (i) projection of the working area including liquid level and printing layer upon the holder. c) Image of the working area and d) a complete view of the bioprinter. (e) Image of the autolevel system showing liquid (blue line) and platform (green line) position detection.

To control the full bioprinting process a custom software had to be developed, which includes the printer protocol, for making the system easy to use for non-expert operators. The printing protocol has multiple steps: For printing a multi-material model, the model must first be sliced, generating a stack of images, one for each layer, and a material is assigned to each layer. For this task, a custom software, based on the slicing algorithm described in [11] is used, it takes, as input, the desired model in STL (stereolithography) format, and produces a sequence of images representing the cross-sections of the model, letting the user choose the position, scale, orientation, and distance between layers. When a layer of a given thickness needs to be printed, the platform is submerged in the bioink in such a way that the offset between the support, or the model if previous layers already exist, and the level of the bioink is equal to the layer thickness.

If the layer is required to be of a different material than the previous one, the platform is lifted from the vat, the revolver rotates, placing the vat with the desired material under the platform, it is lowered again, and the next layer

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2 is projected. As the material is consumed during printing, the level of the liquid in each vat is different, therefore
3 the platform needs to be positioned in such a way that the difference between the top surface of the partially printed
4 model and the surface of the bioink is equal to the desired layer thickness. This work describes the method that
5 allows automating the process that determines how much the support/model should be immersed so that the
6 difference between it and the bioink surface is the height of the layer.
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10 2.2 AI liquid level detection techniques

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12 The process of detecting the offset between model/platform and liquid surface comprises several associated
13 processes, which, in the literature, have been independently approached, such as detection of liquid in a container
14 or object detection. In particular, the utilization of AI and computer vision techniques for liquid level detection
15 has been extensively explored, its most frequent applications include the automation of chemical experiments [12],
16 [13], [14], [15], and the monitoring of water level in rivers, dams, canals and reservoirs [16], [17], [18].
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21 Eppel [12] proposes a computer vision method for tracing liquid level and material boundaries in transparent
22 vessels, based on the graph cut algorithm. This method is capable of tracing unrestricted boundary shapes, making
23 it applicable to solids and powders as well. It can find the globally optimal solution in real-time, and has a
24 strong theoretical background, but requires the pre-definition of regions corresponding to each phase (material and
25 air) by the printer's human operator. Moreover, defining constraints to the boundary shape is challenging. Eppel
26 and Kachman [13] describe a method specifically intended for liquids, assuming that the shape of the
27 boundary is a line or a horizontal ellipse. This method involves generating all possible liquid boundaries
28 (horizontal ellipses inside the container's bounds) and determining the most likely one using indicators such as
29 intensity, intensity change, or edges obtained through edge detection algorithms. Eppel, Xu et al. [14] proposed
30 a machine learning-based approach using a convolutional neural network (CNN) trained on a dataset of 2187
31 images of materials in a chemistry lab or other general settings. This method can segment both vessels and the
32 materials contained in them, in any phase (liquid, solid, powder, foam, etc.), eliminating the need for manually
33 selecting the position of the vat containing the liquid, which is inherent in other explored approaches. However,
34 since it employs deep learning instead of classical computer vision algorithms, it requires a larger amount of
35 computational power to run in real-time, and a large, labeled dataset is necessary to achieve good accuracy. Zepel
36 et al. [15] devised a system aimed at monitoring and closed-loop control of liquid level in chemical experiments,
37 using peristaltic pumps and a webcam. The liquid level is ascertained through the application of a Canny edge
38 detector, using morphological operations to eliminate noise and isolate horizontal lines. The selection process
39 involves choosing the horizontal slice of the image with the highest number of edge pixels. This system
40 effectively obviates the necessity for periodic manual oversight of experiments, a task that, in certain instances,
41 could extend beyond 48 hours. Furthermore, it includes an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI) for
42 straightforward parameter configuration and integrates seam-lessly with the Slack chat platform, providing a
43 convenient remote monitoring system. Bruinink et al. [16] presented a novel approach for detecting and measuring
44 water levels in images of staff gauges. Their method leverages a random forest classifier, using a feature vector
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of textons to segment the gauge. Gaussian Mixture Model segmentation is employed for isolating digits and bars, followed by a random forest classifier for digit recognition and shape moments for bar detection. To ascertain the water level, another random forest classifier is applied, segmenting the image into two classes: staff-gauge and water. This method was tested on different water canals in the Netherlands, using images captured with a mobile device, and can achieve a precision of above 97% even in the face of changing environmental conditions, reflections, and dirt on the gauge and water. Muhadi et al. [17] introduced an alternative approach for water level estimation, based on semantic segmentation with convolutional neural networks (CNN). The evaluation considered DeepLabv3+ and SegNet networks, revealing that DeepLabv3+ outperformed with an impressive accuracy and Intersection over Union (IoU) exceeding 90%, along with an 80% boundary score. The water level estimates derived from this method were cross-referenced with readings from a level sensor, resulting in a Spearman's rank-order correlation coefficient of 0.91, indicating a substantial correlation. Consequently, this proposed method emerges as a viable solution for water level measurement, particularly in cases where a dedicated water level sensor is not available. Lin et al. [18] performed water level measurement through edge detection, specifically using the Hough transform to delineate the water line. Photogrammetric techniques, including the collinearity equations, are then applied to convert the acquired position in image space to object space. This conversion takes into consideration both internal factors (such as focal length, location of the principal point, and lens distortion) and external factors (comprising position and orientation) of the camera. Their method achieves a high accuracy of 0.01 mm in detecting water levels using single camera images. Remarkably, it demonstrates reliability even in challenging conditions, such as camera movement and noise induced by rain.

2.3 Computer vision technique

As mentioned earlier, the process of detecting the offset between the model/platform and the liquid surface involves two associated processes: the liquid level and the model/platform detection. Each process must be developed individually, and the results compared in the final steps to determine the offset. Figure 2 summarizes the steps performed for the offset calculation, including these two processes.

2.3.1 Liquid level detection

We have adopted a paradigm grounded in classical computer vision techniques, specifically edge detection. This approach is inspired by a combination of techniques highlighted in the introduction, notably [15] and [18]. While it is true that more sophisticated methods based on deep learning have gained prominence recently, our results demonstrate that the precision achieved with our chosen method is more than sufficient for addressing the specific problem at hand. Moreover, it comes with significantly lower computational requirements and does not necessitate a large dataset for pre-training. Computational efficiency holds particular importance in our scenario, as the level detection process must be executed in real time during the printing process. Despite the availability of more advanced methods, our approach strikes a practical balance between precision and computational demands, aligning well with the real-time constraints inherent in our application. (See process below and in Figure 2a)

- 1) Convert the image to grayscale, as color information is not relevant for detecting edges. Grayscale conversion simplifies the image by eliminating color variations, allowing edge detection algorithms to focus solely on intensity differences. This step enhances the efficiency of edge detection processes, as color details are often unnecessary and may introduce additional complexity without contributing significantly to the edge detection task.
- 2) Implement contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) to enhance the contrast of the image, thereby increasing the accuracy of edge detection. CLAHE is a method that improves local contrast by redistributing pixel intensities. This is particularly beneficial for images with varying illumination levels or uneven contrast as ours, as it ensures that edges and details are more pronounced, therefore providing a better foundation for subsequent edge detection algorithms.
- 3) Apply the Canny edge detection technique after computing the optimal parameters derived from the median intensity of the image. This method involves determining the appropriate parameters for Canny edge detection based on the median intensity of the image, ensuring a more adaptive and effective approach. Canny edge detection is a widely used algorithm in computer vision for detecting edges in images [19]. By leveraging the median intensity, we can dynamically adjust the parameters, enhancing the algorithm's performance across a variety of image conditions [15]. This step contributes to the overall robustness and accuracy of edge detection in the subsequent stages of image processing.
- 4) Apply morphological dilation to eliminate noise from the image. Morphological dilation is a technique used in image processing to expand the boundaries of objects, which helps in smoothing and connecting regions. By applying dilation, small, isolated noise pixels can be suppressed, resulting in a cleaner image. This step is crucial for improving the quality of subsequent processing steps, as it reduces the impact of unwanted artifacts and enhances the overall robustness of the image analysis.
- 5) Implement morphological opening using a rectangular structuring element to extract horizontal lines from the image. Since the surface of the liquid is consistently in the horizontal plane, vertical edges become irrelevant and can be disregarded. By utilizing a rectangular structuring element, this process helps emphasize and isolate the horizontal components in the image, enhancing the focus on relevant features for further analysis.
- 6) Determine the location of the strongest horizontal lines by dividing the previously obtained edge image in 4px high slices (equivalent to approximately 0.092 mm) and calculating the ratio of white pixels to total pixels in each slice. Given that the meniscus of the liquid has a certain thickness that might affect measurement consistency, we opt for the bottommost slice with a ratio exceeding a specified threshold. This selection is made with the bottom of the meniscus serving as a reference point. By employing this approach, we account for the potential thickness of the meniscus, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the measurement by focusing on the most prominent horizontal features in the image.

2.3.2 *Platform position detection*

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2 To detect the position of the printing platform, we opted for a naive Bayes classifier as our chosen model due
3 to its low computational requirements and satisfactory performance, provided that the color of the platform is
4 sufficiently distinct from the liquid and background. During training, a single image with a manually labeled
5 segmentation mask was employed. Utilizing a simple model and requiring only a small amount of training
6 data, the model can be swiftly retrained to accommodate various lighting conditions or a platform of a different
7 color. The pipeline employed consists of the following steps (Figure 2b):
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- 11 1) Implement a binary classification model at the pixel level, facilitating the segmentation of the image into
12 distinct regions representing the printing platform and the background based on color characteristics. This
13 approach involves classifying each pixel as either belonging to the platform or the background, creating a
14 clear and delineated separation.
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- 17 2) Perform morphological opening to filter out spurious detected areas, such as those caused by reflections.
18 This process helps eliminate undesired artifacts and enhances the accuracy of the detection by refining the
19 boundaries of identified regions. Specifically, morphological opening involves a combination of erosion
20 followed by dilation, effectively smoothing and removing small, noise-like features. With this step, we aim
21 to improve the segmentation robustness results minimizing the impact of unwanted visual disturbances.
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23
- 24 3) Identify the position of the bottommost pixel in the obtained segmentation mask as the location of the
25 bottom of the printing platform. Selecting the bottom edge as the reference point is preferred due to its
26 stability. In contrast, the top edge of the segmentation mask corresponds to the back of the platform, whose
27 apparent position may vary based on the camera angle. Additionally, the top edge may include the rod
28 connecting the platform and motor, necessitating an extra step for its removal. By choosing the stable
29 bottom edge, we enhance accuracy and simplify the subsequent analysis by avoiding potential variations
30 introduced by camera perspectives and extraneous elements.
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- 33 4) Compute the position of the topmost edge of the platform by adding the known and fixed height of the
34 platform. This position is the relevant one, because the model is constructed on top of the platform, and
35 consequently, the gap between it and the liquid surface determines the layer height.
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Figure 2: Flowchart of the a) liquid level position and b) platform level position detection. c) Relationship between liquid position and measured liquid height value, and d) Relationship between platform position and measured platform height value. e) Image of the system detected liquid and platform position.

2.4 Deep Learning-Based technique.

As mentioned above, an alternative method based on deep learning was tested, for both the platform and liquid level detection tasks. In this case, semantic segmentation based on convolutional neural networks was applied. This kind of neural network is capable of solving a wide variety of image-based tasks with an outstanding performance and allows generalization to varied environments without requiring manual tuning as is sometimes required for classical computer vision approaches. However, the application of this technique requires an image dataset with which to train the network. Due to the uniqueness of bioprinting, there are no image databases, and it is necessary to develop it.

For solving the platform detection task, two network architectures have been evaluated for solving this problem. The first one (Model 1) is a fully connected CNN with a pretrained ResNet101 encoder backbone, which has been trained by Eppel et al. on Vector-LabPics, a dataset containing images of various materials of chemical vessels. [14] This model has been chosen because it has already been trained for semantic segmentation tasks including the recognition of glass vessels and liquid contained inside them, allowing for its direct application to the liquid level detection subtask. However, the printing platform is specific to our setup, and therefore applying this model to platform position detection requires retraining on a custom dataset.

The main shortcoming of CNN-based detection with respect to classical computer vision methods are the requirement of a great volume of labelled images in order to achieve satisfactory performance, and the increased computational requirements, which impedes real-time execution of the system in an embedded system. Therefore, a simplified CNN architecture (Model 2) was also evaluated. This architecture consists of a reduced version of UNet [20] which is capable of performing segmentation tasks with both significantly reduced training time, and inference time.

2.4.1 Dataset Preparation

To collect a set of images of the process, we implemented a recording feature in our 3D printer's control software, which automatically stores a video with the integrated camera every time a model is printed. This recording includes additional metadata such as the position of the Z-axis motor and the layer being printed during each frame of the video. We subsequently performed several printing tests and preprocessed the resulting recordings into a dataset suitable for neural network training. This preprocessing involved filtering out frames where the z-axis motor was moving and generating a synthetic segmentation mask for the platform from the motor position. The relationship between pixels in the camera image and the motor's position was estimated through linear interpolation from a few manually measured points. The extracted frames were also cropped to the size of the printing vat, eliminating extraneous information that increases computational load and may confound the network. The resulting dataset contains 27.115 images extracted from 46 videos, covering different combinations of printed models, resin colors, and platform colors. In total, four resin pigments (green, blue, yellow and red) and two

platform colors (white and red) are included.

After performing the preprocessing, an 80-10-10 train/validation/test split was performed. The split was performed on the basis of complete videos as opposed to individual extracted images, as image-wise splitting may result in adjacent, and therefore nearly identical, frames being split into different sets, leading to undetected overfitting of the model due to similarity between training and validation/test sets. The final dataset contains 19289 samples from 36 videos in the train set, 4147 samples from 4 videos in the validation set, and 3679 samples from 6 videos in the test set. The videos have different resolutions, ranging from 640x480 through 1280x720. As the images are subsequently cropped to remove the background, keeping only the region containing the vat, the sizes of the final images in the dataset range from 333 to 538 pixels in width and 229 to 364 pixels in height.

In order to evaluate the accuracy of platform and liquid level detection and compare the tested methods, we generated an additional dataset (henceforth referred to as “sweep dataset”) by sequentially moving the printing platform in 0.1 mm increments, and taking a picture of each position, with a variety of resin pigmentations and platform colors. The collected images cover a total of four liquid colorings (clear, red, yellow and blue) and two platform colors (white and blue). The use of this additional dataset allows for a rigorous analysis of positional accuracy, and on the other hand enables the assessment of generalizability to different printing conditions. In particular, it includes samples with clear resin (only PEGDA and photoinitiator, with no pigment), which is the most common case in bioprinting applications. This dataset is not employed in training of the models and therefore serves as an additional test set to evaluate the resilience of the models to changes in conditions, though it does not reflect actual printing conditions as accurately as the main dataset, given that no image projection or resin polymerization takes place during its generation. These images have a resolution of 3840x2160 pixels, with the regions of interest being between 1586-1658 pixels of width and 1007-1063 pixels of height.

2.4.2 Liquid Level Detection.

Detection of liquid level is performed in two steps: first, a binary segmentation mask representing the area of the liquid in the image is obtained through the application of a CNN-based segmentation model; then, the obtained mask is analyzed to obtain the position of the top edge of the liquid in pixels.

In order to obtain the segmentation mask, we use the model from [14], as it is trained for detection of liquid, among other states of matter, on chemical environments, which are similar enough to our environment (vat containing liquid in the bioprinter), so that this model achieves sufficient performance. Then, the level is obtained through selection of the topmost line in the resulting binary image that surpasses a defined threshold of liquid-containing pixels. Datasets for liquid segmentation, and models trained on them, are widely available and therefore no bespoke training is required for this subtask.

We studied the accuracy of this method by manually labeling the liquid position in three sample frames from each video in the training dataset and comparing the manually indicated position with the one returned by both the edge detection-based method described in Section 2.3.1 and the method described here. All videos are included with no

train/test split, as none of the tested methods have been trained on this data, and therefore there is no risk of overfitting. To ensure the selected frames reflect the widest variety of situations, they are chosen according to platform position: one frame where the platform is at the top, one where it is at the median position across all frames, and one where it is at the bottommost position. This also ensures the liquid levels differ, as the immersion of the platform displaces the fluid. Labeling every frame would require a significant manual effort, and the nature of video data implies that subsequent frames almost always have an equal or very similar fluid level, therefore providing mostly redundant information. **Figure 3** shows the result of this comparison.

Figure 3. a) Comparison of liquid position predictions vs. ground truth. b) Quantitative performance metrics of the prediction models, reporting the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the root mean squared error (RMSE, in pixels) for the edge-detection approach and the CNN (Model 1).

Our edge detection-based algorithm proved to have a better performance both with respect to accuracy and to computational performance, and said performance is more than satisfactory enough for the proposed task (if we assume the 43.32 px/mm ratio of our test setup, the 5.572 px RMSE is equivalent to 0.13 mm, roughly equivalent to our layer size). Therefore, we have elected not to train Model 2 on the liquid detection task, as, given that it is a smaller model, its accuracy would probably be equal or worse than that of Model 1.

2.4.3 Platform Position Detection.

Detecting the platform, on the other hand, is a highly specific task of our setup, and there are no works in the literature that make use of a platform with a similar appearance to the one used in ours. Therefore, as described in section 2.4.1, we have had to prepare a dataset of annotated images for the platform segmentation task. Model 1 is trained on the previously described dataset, using the pre-trained model weights from [13] as a starting point,

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2 and Model 2 is trained on the same dataset with no pre-trained weights. For training and evaluating the models,
3 we used an 80-10-10 train-validation-test split, as described in Section 2.4.1. The CNN models are implemented
4 in PyTorch, using CUDA for GPU acceleration of training, and the DirectML API for GPU acceleration of
5 inference on the target 3D printer control computer, while the remaining image processing operations are
6 performed using OpenCV. The camera resolution was set to 1920x1080 pixels, with the region of interest (the vat
7 containing the liquid) being 781x313 pixels. For the tiny model, the cropped image is subsequently scaled to
8 256x256, further reducing computational requirements.
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13 To obtain a platform position from the segmentation mask produced by the models, a morphological opening
14 operation is performed on the mask and the largest connected component in the result is selected, in order to
15 remove spurious detections, which will generally be smaller than the desired platform area. Finally, the
16 bottommost row of the image that surpasses a certain proportion of white pixels is selected as the platform position.
17 The bottom edge is used because of its greater positional stability, but we are interested in the top edge of the
18 platform, so a constant offset, determined by applying the RANSAC algorithm [21] on the collected experimental
19 data, is added. RANSAC has been used because it ignores outlier points in the data, caused by spurious detections
20 in certain regions of the position space.
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27 We perform a theoretical comparison of the dimensional accuracy of the classical computer vision-based and
28 CNN-based methods by applying all methods on two subsets of the sweep dataset representing the most common
29 pigmentations in biofabrication applications: clear (no pigment) and yellow (tartrazine). In both cases a blue
30 platform is used, as it provides maximum contrast with the used resins. Given that the color of the platform can be
31 arbitrarily chosen and has no bearing on the printing results, but is significant for computer vision methods, which
32 rely on sufficient contrast between parts of the image to be distinguished apart, it is advisable to select a color that
33 is maximally different from other elements in the region of interest, such as the vat, resin or base.
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Figure 4. Comparison of platform position predictions vs. ground truth for blue platform and yellow resin. a) full position range. b) only region with submerged platform.

Figure 5. Comparison of platform position predictions vs. ground truth for blue platform and clear resin. a) full position range. b) only region with submerged platform.

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4 Figures 4 and 5 plot the platform positions in pixels obtained by each of the three tested methods (naïve Bayes
5 classifier, FCN with ImageNet backbone – Model 1, and UNET – Model 2) against the ground truth position,
6 computed by manually labeling the top and bottom positions in the image sequence and interpolating between
7 them with the platform position in millimeters given by the stepper motor that moves the platform, as described
8 in Section 2.4.1.
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12 When interpreting the results, it is necessary to distinguish two regions of operation: in the first region (<600 px
13 for Figure 4 and <500 px for Figure 5), the platform is inside the vat but outside the liquid, and in the second
14 region, it is fully submerged in the liquid. Only the second region is of interest for the liquid-platform alignment
15 problem that is the subject of this paper, though both are included in the charts for completeness. During the
16 printing process, the platform will only be outside the liquid when printing begins and when a material switch is
17 performed; therefore, almost every image in the printing video dataset, used for training the deep learning-based
18 approaches, will be in the second region. The sweep dataset, on the other hand, fully covers both regions, as a full
19 sweep over the platform position space has been done.
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26 For yellow resin (Figure 4), both the Bayes model and CNN model 2 mistakenly detect the resin instead of the
27 platform when it is outside. The cause of this is that, as mentioned, the models are mostly trained on images from
28 the region of interest, inside the resin, and the apparent color of the platform changes when it is submerged, taking
29 on a yellowish-green tint (Figure 6b). Therefore, in the first operating region, the color that the models attempt to
30 detect is closer to the yellow of the liquid than the unmodified blue of the platform. On the other hand, when the
31 platform is under the liquid, all the tested methods produce very good results.
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36 For the clear resin (Figure 5), the Bayes model gives exceptionally good results both above and below the liquid,
37 failing only at the transition point between both regions. The cause of this is that the liquid meniscus occludes the
38 platform, impeding its detection (Figure 6c). CNN Model 1, on the other hand, shows a very high variance, while
39 Model 2 mistakenly detects the bottom of the platform in the 300-550 px region and the liquid line in the 600-650
40 px region, though it is accurate between 550 and 600 px. This shows that the deep learning-based models suffer a
41 drop in performance when they are applied to liquid colors that are not represented in their training data,
42 necessitating the collection of a large amount of images from the desired environment, while the Bayes model can
43 be adapted to new conditions by training on a single sample image.
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Figure 6. Sample images for blue platform and yellow resin. a) platform outside liquid (region 1), b) platform inside liquid (region 2). c) Liquid meniscus occluding the platform.

2.6 Code Availability

The source code for this project is available at GitHub: [cogradeusc/bioprinter-level-detection](https://github.com/cogradeusc/bioprinter-level-detection)

2.7 Evaluation of Auto-Leveling Performance in Multimaterial 3D Printing

To evaluate the performance of the developed software in 3D printing, cylindrical models were fabricated using a polyethylene glycol diacrylate (PEGDA) solution (30 % w/v) containing 0.1 % w/v LAP as a photoinitiator and 0.05 % w/v tartrazine as a photoabsorber; with 3 different colorants: yellow (tartrazine), red and green. The printing process was carried out under two conditions: (i) manual adjustment of the printing position and (ii) using the auto-level option provided by the software. The printing parameters set on the printer were as follows: **UV light intensity:** 21.5 mW/cm² **Exposure time:** 5 seconds **Layer thickness:** 100 μ m **Material distribution:** 20 layers of yellow material, 10 layers of red material, and 20 layers of green material. After each print, images of the models were captured using a magnifying glass. The thickness of each layer, the color sections, and the overall structure were measured using ImageJ software. Experiments were performed in triplicate (n=3).

2.8 Optimization and validation of photocurable ink formulations

2.8.1 Evaluation of printing fidelity using PEGDA inks.

To assess the printing resolution of printed structures using PEGDA-based inks, CAD model in the shape of a five-pointed star was created. Four different ink formulations were prepared. Two consisted of PEGDA solutions at 10% v/v containing either 0.1% w/v LAP or 0.05% w/v LAP. The other two consisted of PEGDA solutions at 5% v/v, each containing the same LAP concentrations as in the previous case. All formulations contained a constant tartrazine concentration of 0.025% w/v. A printing parameter sweep was performed to ensure that the optimal range for each ink formulation was not excluded. The following printing parameters were tested: **UV light intensities:** 7.5 mW/cm², 12.5 mW/cm², 17.8 mW/cm² and 25.3 mW/cm² **Exposure times:** from 2 seconds to 28 seconds depending on the ink **Layer thickness:** 100 µm. Printing fidelity was determined by comparing the dimensions of the printed models to those of the original CAD design using a specialized software designed on our lab. All experiments were performed in triplicate (n = 3).

2.8.2 Stiffness tuning via tartrazine concentration

To further characterize the PEGDA-based inks, stiffness was evaluated for four formulations consisting of 10% v/v PEGDA solutions containing 0.1% w/v LAP. Tartrazine was incorporated at four different concentrations: 0.0125% w/v, 0.025% w/v, 0.05% w/v and 0.1% w/v, to assess its effect on construct stiffness under different printing conditions. Printing was performed using two parameter sets: (i) **UV light intensity:** 12.5 mW/cm² **Exposure time:** 12 seconds, and (ii) **UV light intensity:** 25.2 mW/cm² **Exposure time:** 5 seconds. These printing parameters sets were previously determined to be optimal for inks containing 0.025% w/v and 0.05% w/v tartrazine, respectively. The printed cylinder models were fabricated with a layer thickness of 0.1 mm for the first layer and 0.2 µm for subsequent layers. Following fabrication, the stiffness of each construct was measured using a Mechanical Tester Model Mach-1 (Biomomentum Inc, Canada) using the stress relaxation mode

2.8.3 Printing of complex 3D structure.

To assess the printability of complex structures, a multi-material hollow model was fabricated consisting of a main channel with an inner diameter of 1.125 mm that branched into three channels with inner diameters of 375 µm, 675 µm and 750 µm. Wall thicknesses were 563 µm for the main channel and 375 µm, 225 µm and 188 µm for the respective branches. Three ink formulations were prepared, each consisting of 10% v/v PEGDA, 0.1% w/v LAP and 0.05% w/v tartrazine, with different dyes: yellow (tartrazine), red and green. Printing was performed using the following parameters: **UV light intensity:** 25.2 mW/cm² **Exposure time:** 5 seconds for the yellow ink, 6 seconds for the red ink, and 7 seconds for the green ink **Layer thickness:** 100 µm **Material distribution:** 12 layers of green material, 13 layers of red material, and 27 layers of yellow material. After fabrication, images of

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2 the structures were captured using a magnifying glass to assess structural integrity.

3 4 2.9 Cell Bioprinting

5 6 2.9.1 Cell Sourcing

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8 Human fibroblasts (HFF-2), Cardiomyoblasts (H9c2), and human osteosarcoma cells (SaOs-2) were used in this
9 study. All cell lines were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM; Gibco), supplemented with
10 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Capricorn Scientific) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich), under
11 standard culture conditions (37 °C, 5% CO₂). Upon reaching approximately 80% confluence, cells were
12 subcultured using 0.25% trypsin-EDTA (Sigma-Aldrich). For subsequent identification within the constructs,
13 H9c2 cells were pre-labeled with CellTracker™ Orange CMTMR (Invitrogen), and SaOS-2 cells with
14 CellTracker™ Blue CMAC (Invitrogen), whereas HFF-2 cells were used unlabeled.
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19 20 2.9.2 Preparation of Bioinks

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22 A GelMA solution was prepared by dissolving GelMA powder in complete DMEM and adding LAP (Apollo
23 Scientific) at a final concentration of 0.05% w/v. Three distinct bioinks were formulated by mixing the GelMA
24 solution with each cell type separately, at a final cell concentration of 1×10^6 cells/mL.
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27 28 2.9.3 Bioprinting Procedure

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30 A cylindrical structure of 3 mm height and 6 mm diameter was designed, with a layer thickness of 100 µm. The
31 printing parameters were set to 5 seconds of exposure per layer and a light intensity of 15.1 mW/cm². Immediately
32 after printing, the hydrogel constructs were covered with culture medium and incubated under standard conditions
33 (37 °C, 5% CO₂) for up to 5 days.
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36 37 2.9.4 Cell Viability Assay

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39 Cell viability within the bioprinted constructs was assessed at days 1 and 5 post-printing using the Live/Dead Cell
40 Imaging Kit (Sigma-Aldrich). Briefly, samples were washed twice with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS;
41 Sigma-Aldrich) and stained with Calcein-AM, Propidium iodide, and Hoechst 33342, following the
42 manufacturer's instructions. Samples were incubated for 60 minutes in the dark, and fluorescence images were
43 acquired using a fluorescence microscope (MATEO FL, Leica). Image analysis was performed using FIJI (ImageJ)
44 software and CellProfiler 4.2.8. The experiment was performed in triplicate (n = 3).
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52 The data collected in this work was presented as mean ± SD and statistically analyzed by one way analysis of
53 variance with GraphPad Prism. The differences were considered to be statistically significant when the p values
54 were less than 0.05.
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57 58 **3. Discussion and results.**

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In this section, the results are presented and discussed from two key perspectives. First, the computational performance of the onboard system integrated into the bioprinter is evaluated. Specifically, the feasibility of using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for real-time liquid level detection was assessed. Due to high computational demands and latency issues, it was concluded that CNN-based approaches are currently not suitable for scalable implementation in this context. Consequently, the second part focuses on the evaluation of the computer vision-based detection system currently employed in the bioprinter. This lightweight, image processing approach demonstrated reliable, real-time performance and robust accuracy, making it suitable for automated multimaterial bioprinting tasks.

The capabilities of the complete system were validated through the fabrication of two biologically relevant tissue models: a vascular-like construct, featuring spatially separated channels and multiple bioinks to mimic hierarchical vessel structures, and a multilayered skin tissue model, incorporating distinct layers of fibroblasts and keratinocytes to replicate dermal and epidermal organization. These models confirm the system's potential for producing complex, structured, and viable tissue constructs suitable for use in regenerative medicine and in vitro testing platforms.

3.1 Computer performance comparison

The sensitivity of the system's computational cost was evaluated by comparing a high-complexity architecture (Model 1) against a significantly reduced version (Model 2) designed to minimize the number of layers and parameters. Despite reducing the input resolution and the model depth, the hardware latency for CNN-based inference did not reach the threshold required for seamless real-time integration (60 FPS). To evaluate the suitability of the deep learning-based approaches we implemented for the real-time detection task at hand, we benchmarked and compared classical computer vision methods and CNN-based methods for liquid level detection. This test was performed on the same PC we use for controlling the printer in production. Table 1 shows the obtained results. The classical method has a runtime of under 16 ms, making it capable of running in real time at a frame rate of 60 FPS. In contrast, the CNN-based approach is approximately 80 times slower when using the CPU, and 32 times slower with GPU acceleration. It can only achieve a maximum frame rate of 2 FPS, which is unsuitable for real-time analysis during the printing process.

Table 1: Per-frame execution times for liquid level detection.

Method	Time (ms)
Classic CPU	15.952
CNN CPU	1290.436
CNN GPU	509.242

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2 The result shows that the CNN-based technique can detect both the vat and the resin with accuracy similar than
3 the previous one. However, it is much more computationally demanding than the edge detection-based algorithm,
4 with the largest tested model requiring approximately 400 ms to process a frame on a GPU and upwards of 2
5 seconds when running on a CPU. In contrast, our computer vision-based method takes around 40 ms without GPU
6 acceleration.
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9 10 3.2 Measurement accuracy

11 Once the use of CNN has been ruled out for reasons of computational performance, this section shows the quality
12 of the measurement referred to the computer vision system. To evaluate the measurement accuracy of the
13 developed method for platform detection, we used the sweep dataset, collected as described in Section 2.4.1, by
14 moving the platform in 0.1 mm increments, and compared its theoretical position, defined through the stepper
15 motor controller, with the position measured by our algorithm, in pixels. A blue platform and clear resin were
16 used, representing the most common use case in bioprinting. The method is very accurate, achieving a Pearson
17 correlation coefficient of 0.994 between the obtained measurement and the actual platform position. The values
18 given are in pixels, but they can be converted into a position value in millimeters by using the coefficient given by
19 performing linear regression on the obtained measurements, which in this case is 43.35 px/mm, though it will vary
20 depending on the setup used, including the camera's resolution and distance to the vat.
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28 The main shortcoming that can be observed is that position measurement is not accurate when the platform is
29 partially dipped in the vat or the liquid, because, as described in Section 2.4.3, refraction causes the image of the
30 platform to be displaced and the meniscus or the edge of the vat occlude the platform, which prevents the algorithm
31 from detecting a part of it. If the position ranges where the platform overlaps the edge of the vat or liquid are
32 ignored, the achieved correlation coefficient increases to 0.999. As the region of interest for solving the problem
33 at hand is the range between the liquid meniscus and the bottom of the platform, this means that a very high
34 accuracy can be achieved for the relevant position range.
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39 As for the estimation of liquid level, our edge detection-based method can achieve a theoretical precision of 4px
40 because of the slicing process performed in the algorithm (Section 2.3.1, step 6), which according to the previously
41 computed conversion factor, leads to a physical measurement precision of 0.092 mm, with our printer and camera
42 setup. Figure 3b shows the result of an empirical comparison of accuracy between the computer vision and CNN
43 method on frames extracted from real videos of the printing process. As previously explained in Section 2.4.2, the
44 edge detection-based method achieves an RMSE of 5.572 px, giving a measurement accuracy of 0.13 mm, close
45 to the maximum achievable precision, while the CNN approach has an RMSE of 9.431 px, equivalent to 0.22 mm.
46 Therefore, the edge detection method is both more accurate and faster.
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52 53 3.3 Evaluation of Auto-Leveling Performance in Multimaterial 3D Printing

54 To evaluate the performance of the auto-leveling system, cylindrical models composed of three stacked segments
55 were fabricated, each printed with a resin of a different color. This geometry was selected as a representative
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multimaterial structure to assess both dimensional accuracy and geometric fidelity. Figure 7a shows representative images of structures printed with the auto-leveling strategy, where a smooth and well-defined cylindrical shape is observed, with clearly distinguishable material segments and uniform layer stacking.

Figure 7: Image of a cylindrical structure with three segments, each composed of resin with a distinct colorant a) using auto-leveling strategy, and i) magnification area showing the layer thickness uniformity, and b) adjusting manually the printing level (i) shows the imperfection using this approximation). c) Data analysis of total and segment height. d) Data analysis: layer thickness biomaterial/biomaterial interface uniformity using auto-leveling method. All the experiments have a n=3.

For comparison, the same model was printed using a manually adjusted build platform. As shown in Figure 7b, the samples fabricated without auto-leveling exhibit noticeable geometric distortions, especially at the interfaces between the different materials. These include non-uniform diameters, layer misalignment, and local bulging, indicating a loss of cylindrical symmetry. These distortions highlight the limitations of operator-dependent manual leveling, which introduces local height variations in the print area and compromises geometric consistency.

The quantitative analysis of the printed structures is summarized in Figure 7c, which presents measurements of the total height and segment thickness for each material. While both configurations produced structures within the same dimensional order of magnitude, the automatic leveling strategy showed less variability in all measured parameters. Although small systematic deviations from the nominal design values were observed, these deviations

1
2 were consistent and reproducible, indicating greater process stability. Importantly, systematic deviations can be
3 effectively compensated for through calibration, given that high variability inherently limits the reliability and
4 reproducibility of print.
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7 On the other hand, our experiments focused also on the specific behavior of the two adjacent layers where material
8 transitions occurred using auto-leveling position. The results, shown in figure 7d, revealed significant dimensional
9 variations between the intended and actual layer thicknesses with deviations from the original target value of 100
10 μm (Green/red: 0.957 and Red/Yellow: 1.119). These discrepancies were found to be material-dependent,
11 suggesting that factors such as the light absorption properties of each biomaterial, influenced by the presence of
12 colorants, play a critical role in the final printed dimensions.
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16 Specifically, materials with higher light absorption appeared to exhibit more pronounced variations, affecting the
17 accuracy of layer deposition. The yellow and green inks have absorption spectra with maximum peaks close to
18 405 nm, the emission wavelength of the DLP projector [21]. By strongly absorbing in this spectrum region, a
19 larger fraction of the incident light is retained by the dyes, reducing the energy that ultimately reaches the
20 photoactive molecules responsible for crosslinking [22]. Consequently, thinner layers are formed compared to
21 those obtained with the red ink, whose absorption peak is located around 550 nm [21], allowing a greater amount
22 of energy at 405 nm to reach the photoinitiator and promote a higher curing thickness.
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26 This variation highlights the complexity of multi-material bioprinting, where factors like material properties, light
27 exposure, and AI-driven auto-level adjustments must be carefully considered for achieving optimal precision. The
28 findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how material characteristics influence the bioprinting process
29 and emphasize the need for further refinement in both AI algorithms and material formulations to enhance the
30 reliability and accuracy of multi-material DLP bioprinting systems.
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33 *3.4 Optimization and validation of photocurable ink formulations*

34 *3.4.1 Evaluation of printing fidelity*

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36 Printing fidelity was evaluated using a five-pointed star model, selected because, despite its apparently simple
37 geometry, the accurate reproduction of sharp tips and narrow features represents a demanding task for DLP-based
38 printing. Achieving high fidelity in this geometry requires precise control over light penetration and
39 polymerization confinement, making it a sensitive benchmark for assessing printing performance.
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43 Figure 8 presents the similarity analysis in the frontal plane for the four PEGDA-based inks tested at four different
44 DLP light intensities. For each formulation, exposure times were systematically varied in order to identify the
45 printing parameters that yielded the highest percentage of similarity with respect to the original CAD model.
46 Similarity was quantified using an in-house image analysis algorithm developed in Python, which compares the
47 dimensions of the printed structures to the reference design (figure 8a).
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51 As expected, lower DLP light intensities generally required longer exposure times to achieve higher printing
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2 fidelity. This behavior is consistent with the fundamental principles of photopolymerization, where a reduction in
3 irradiance must be compensated by increased exposure time to reach a sufficient degree of conversion and
4 crosslinking density for stable feature formation. These results confirm that an appropriate balance between light
5 intensity and exposure time is critical for accurately reproducing fine geometrical features.
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9 In Figure 8f, the same analysis is shown for the four ink formulations prepared without tartrazine, evaluated at
10 three DLP light intensities using the optimal exposure times previously identified. Interestingly, when a suitable
11 combination of exposure time and light intensity was selected, comparable similarity values could be achieved
12 even in the absence of a photoabsorber such as tartrazine, although this trend was not observed uniformly across
13 all formulations. This indicates that while the inclusion of a photoabsorber facilitates polymerization confinement
14 and parameter optimization, high printing fidelity can still be attained under carefully tuned printing conditions
15 depending on the ink composition.
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Figure 8: a) Flowchart of the similarity methodology used. b) bioinks used. c) XY-plane similarity percentage as a function of exposure time for the bioinks used [i) Bioink 1, ii) Bioink 2, iii) Bioink 3 and iv) bioink 4]. d) Bar plots comparing similarity percentages for three different DLP exposure values, contrasting inks with and without tartrazine.

3.4.2 Light absorption modeling in tartrazine-doped photopolymer

To investigate the effect of tartrazine concentration on light absorption in a photopolymer resin used for vat photopolymerization, we modeled the attenuation of 405 nm light using the Beer–Lambert law. The transmitted light intensity at a given depth c is described by:

$$I(c) = I_0 \cdot e^{-ac}$$

where I_0 is the incident light intensity and α is the absorption coefficient, defined as $\alpha = \varepsilon \cdot c$.

Here, ε is the molar absorptivity of tartrazine at 405 nm, taken as $1.79 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ [24], c is the dye concentration in mol/L. For this study, the layer thickness was fixed at 100 μm (0.01 cm), and tartrazine was incorporated into the bioink at concentrations of 0.0125%, 0.025%, 0.05%, and 0.1% w/v. These concentrations correspond to increasing molar concentrations and absorption coefficients, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Light absorption as a function of tartrazine concentration at 100 μm layer thickness (405 nm exposure).

Tartrazine (% w/v)	Concentration (mol/L)	Absorption Coefficient $\alpha(\text{cm}^{-1})$	Transmitted Light (I_0)	Absorbed Light (%)
0.0125	2.34×10^{-4}	4.19	0.943	4.1
0.025	4.68×10^{-4}	8.38	0.889	8.0
0.05	9.36×10^{-4}	16.76	0.789	15.4
0.1	1.87×10^{-3}	33.47	0.621	28.6

As expected, light absorption increased with tartrazine concentration, leading to progressively lower light transmittance across the 100 μm layer. At the lowest concentration (0.0125% w/v), ~4.1% of the light is absorbed, while at 0.1% w/v, nearly 28.6 % of the light is attenuated. By modulating dye concentration, it is possible to optimize cure depth and minimize light overpenetration during layer-by-layer photopolymerization. This modeling framework provides a quantitative tool for resin design in high-resolution 3D printing applications.

Once we confirmed that tartrazine functions as an effective light-absorbing additive at 405 nm, its role was further considered in the context of improving printing precision. Specifically, tartrazine can absorb scattered or excess light within the biomaterial, thereby reducing unintended polymerization outside the target exposure area. This helps prevent overcuring and broadening of features, ultimately contributing to the fabrication of more precise printed structures.

3.4.3 Stiffness tuning via tartrazine concentration

Figure 8d shows the influence of tartrazine concentration on the stiffness of the printed material. As the concentration of tartrazine increases, the printed structures exhibit lower stiffness, consistent with the results previously described in Sections 3.3 and 3.4.2. Tartrazine acts as a photoabsorber, capturing part of the energy emitted by the DLP projector [25]. Consequently, higher concentrations lead to a greater fraction of absorbed light, thereby reducing the amount of energy reaching the photoactive molecules responsible for crosslinking. Since a higher degree of crosslinking is associated with greater stiffness, this phenomenon explains the decrease in stiffness observed at higher tartrazine concentrations. This information is particularly relevant for modulating the mechanical properties of printed materials, especially in applications involving the biofabrication of complex tissues, where the goal is to reproduce mechanical characteristics as close as possible to those of native biological tissues [26].

3.4.4 Multimaterial printability

A complex vascular-like structure composed of three different inks (Figure 9) was fabricated to demonstrate the capabilities of the multi-material printer. Three inks were used (Figure 9a i), which were printed sequentially within a single construct to simulate the transitions and interfaces typical of tissue engineering systems or biomimetic scaffolds.

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a) Multimaterial vascular-like structure model.

- + 0,1% (w/v) LAP + 0,05 % (w/v) Tartrazine + 50µl blue dye
- + 0,1% (w/v) LAP + 0,05 % (w/v) Tartrazine + 50µl red dye
- + 0,1% (w/v) LAP + 0,05% (w/v) Tartrazine

i) Without tartrazine

ii) With tartrazine

d)		CAD model dimension	Average (Printed Dimensions)	Standard deviation	Variability Coefficient	Printing accuracy (%)
Tube A	Inner ϕ (mm)	0,375	0,345	0,045	13,0	92
	Outer ϕ (mm)	0,75	0,651	0,048	7,3	86,8
	Wall thickness	0,1875	0,153	0,033	21,4	81,6
Tube B	Inner ϕ (mm)	0,675	0,646	0,032	5,0	95,7
	Outer ϕ (mm)	1,125	1,044	0,045	4,3	92,8
	Wall thickness	0,225	0,199	0,028	13,9	88,4
Tube C	Inner ϕ (mm)	0,75	0,732	0,050	6,9	97,6
	Outer ϕ (mm)	2,25	1,413	0,018	1,3	62,8
	Wall thickness	0,75	0,341	0,032	9,3	45,4

Figure 9: a) Multimaterial vascular-like structure model: i) inks employed for bioprinting; ii) CAD model including tubular diameters; lateral view of printed constructs using iii) 30% and iv) 10% PEGDA inks, v–vi) top view of the same constructs. b) Stiffness variation of printed constructs as a function of tartrazine concentration.

1
2 c) Resolution comparison of tubular structures printed with and without tartrazine. d) Analysis of the printed
3 structures compared to the CAD model.
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5 Two inks were compared: one with a higher percentage of photopolymerizable polymer (Figure 9a iii and v) and
6 another with a lower percentage (Figure 9a iv and vi). In both cases, the internal channels of the structure remained
7 hollow.
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10 Figure 9d shows an analysis of the printed structures compared to the CAD model (Figure S1). Furthermore, the
11 video (SV1) demonstrates the integrity of the printed wall when an aqueous ink is perfused, confirming a
12 successful printing process in terms of resolution and integrity during material changes. As shown in Figures 8b),
13 i), and ii), the inclusion of tartrazine resulted in sharper and more defined boundaries between materials, especially
14 in the interfacial regions where transitions occurred during printing. Printed structures without tartrazine showed
15 significant blurring or overcuring at the material boundaries, likely due to uncontrolled scattering of light and
16 partial polymerization beyond the intended curing zone.
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22 The improved feature definition observed in the tartrazine-containing structures confirms that the dye plays a
23 crucial role in confining light within the desired exposure regions. By absorbing excess photons that would
24 otherwise initiate unintentional curing, tartrazine enables greater fidelity in pattern creation and prevents crosstalk
25 between adjacent materials during printing transitions. This not only enhances the resolution of fine features but
26 also improves the structural integrity and reproducibility of multi-material constructs.
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30 Overall, these results highlight the dual benefit of using tartrazine: it improves optical control of the curing process
31 and enables more precise multimaterial bioprinting. This control is essential for fabricating functionally graded
32 materials, heterogeneous tissue scaffolds, or organ-on-a-chip platforms, where high-resolution interfaces between
33 materials are crucial for biological performance and function.
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37 These findings emphasize the importance of optimizing both tartrazine concentration and DLP exposure
38 parameters to balance optical attenuation with the desired mechanical outcomes. Careful tuning ensures proper
39 polymer network formation, resulting in structures with tailored stiffness profiles suitable for specific biomedical
40 or engineering applications.
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45 *3.5 Cell Bioprinting*

46 A multimaterial bioprinted cylindrical construct was fabricated using the custom-developed bioprinter,
47 incorporating three different cell types: fibroblasts (HFF2), cardiomyocytes (H9c2), and osteoblasts (SaOs2)
48 (Figure 10).
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Figure 10: Multimaterial bioprinted cylindrical structure. a) i) Image of the printed construct and ii) corresponding 3D CAD model. b) Fluorescence microscopy images: i) HFF2 fibroblasts (green), ii) H9c2 cardiomyocytes (orange), and iii) SaOS-2 osteoblasts (blue) within the 3D construct at 120 h post-printing. Live/Dead staining at v) 24 h and iv) 120 h. vi) Fluorescence image at 24 h without Live/Dead stain. c) Cell viability at 24 and 120 h post-printing.

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2 Figure 10 vi) shows a fluorescence microscopy image acquired 24 hours post-printing, where SaOS-2 cells are
3 labeled in blue and H9c2 in orange, using a 4× magnification. In Figure 9) v), the same structure is visualized
4 using a Live/Dead staining assay. HFF2 appears clearly stained in green, while both SaOS-2 cells and H9c2 show
5 overlapping signals between their respective membrane stains and Calcein AM, indicating good cell viability.
6 Although quantitative viability analysis is challenging in complex 3D structures due to the depth and color
7 variability of the staining, viability was estimated to be approximately 79.7% (Figure 10c). This result is
8 comparable with other values reported for light-based biofabrication methods, where cell damage due to
9 phototoxicity often compromises post-printing survival [27].

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15 Figures 10 b) iv) show the printed constructs after 5 days of incubation. Specifically, in Figure 10 i), HFF2 cells,
16 located in the uppermost layer of the construct, can be clearly observed in green due to their position closer to the
17 imaging surface. Orange-labeled H9c2 cells are visible in the middle layer (Figure 10 ii)), while faint blue regions
18 on the lateral areas correspond to SaOS-2 cells embedded in the deepest layer of the construct (approximately 2
19 mm in depth, Figure 10 iii)). The global cell viability after 5 days was determined to be 86%, which can be
20 attributed to the stabilization of the cells within the supportive hydrogel environment, after UV exposure and
21 handling, and their adaptation to the 3D microenvironment (Figure 9 c).

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27 The spatial organization of the three cell types (fibroblasts at the surface, cardiomyocytes in the middle region,
28 and osteoblasts in the deepest layer) illustrates the capability of the system to reproduce heterogeneous tissue-like
29 structures. This stratification mimics the cellular complexity of native tissues and represents an important step
30 towards the generation of functional in vitro models.

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34 Although quantitative assessment of viability in thick constructs is inherently challenging due to light scattering
35 and overlapping signals in fluorescence microscopy, the results demonstrate that the printing parameters and
36 material system ensured sufficient cytocompatibility to maintain multiple cell types in a confined geometry. These
37 findings support the potential of the developed platform for engineering complex tissues and for establishing
38 multicellular in vitro models for drug testing and regenerative medicine applications.

39 40 41 42 43 **4 Conclusions.**

44 This study addresses key challenges in multi-material DLP bioprinting arising from material-dependent optical
45 and mechanical properties. We demonstrate that variations in layer thickness are strongly influenced by the light
46 absorption characteristics of individual biomaterials, emphasizing the need for improved process control in multi-
47 material printing. To this end, we introduce a computer vision-based gap detection system that enables precise,
48 real-time measurement of the build gap without manual calibration, achieving sub-0.1 mm resolution across a
49 range of resin compositions. In parallel, we validate the use of tartrazine as an effective light-absorbing additive
50 to modulate photopolymerization, reduce overcuring, and enhance interfacial resolution in complex, multi-
51 material constructs. Together, the integration of hardware-level sensing and optical model-guided material
52 formulation provides a scalable and reliable framework for improving accuracy, print fidelity, and versatility in
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1 DLP bioprinting.

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4 Future work will focus on expanding the robustness and generalizability of the proposed system through the
5 collection of a larger and more diverse dataset encompassing variations in illumination conditions, printer
6 configurations, and resin pigmentation. This expanded dataset will support the evaluation of advanced learning-
7 based segmentation approaches, including Transformer-based architectures and foundation models such as the
8 Segment Anything Model (SAM), which offer strong potential for zero-shot or few-shot adaptation without
9 requiring printer-specific training data. These developments are expected to further enhance adaptability, reduce
10 setup dependence, and enable deployment across a broader range of multi-material additive manufacturing
11 platforms.
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